

The Effect of Using WhatsApp on EFL Students' Speech Acts Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>This study examined the effect of using WhatsApp on EFL students' speech acts performance. The participants of the study were 60 male students from two sections of eleventh-grade students from a public school, Fawzi Al-Mulki Secondary School in Al Mafraq, Jordan. An intact section was assigned as a control group taught by the Teacher's Book guidelines. Another section was chosen as an experimental group and was taught WhatsApp according to the instructional program. The training lasted eight weeks during the second semester of the academic year 2021/2022. The instrument used to collect data was a test—the instructional program that offered the participants opportunities to improve their speech acts performance. The findings of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the students' performance on the speech acts test in favor of the students in the experimental group. The improvement in the students' speech acts performance could have resulted from the speech acts activities in which the participants were engaged during the instructional program. The use of WhatsApp offered the participants the chance to interact effectively. Several recommendations were made for EFL teachers, researchers and the Ministry of Education.</i></p>
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Introduction

Nowadays, Teachers of English as a foreign language (TEFL) use CALL in conjunction with information technology. According to (Alsaleem, 2014; Taki and Khazaei, 2011), the last 20 years have seen a technological revolution that has transformed the dynamics of several parts of life and affected how people live and work. The fast advancement and development of data technology have resulted in significantly better and novel teaching techniques. Mobile messaging apps have also been used to help students acquire various language skills and sub-skills such as vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar.

The use of technology in education has changed the way in which teachers deliver the lessons. The sentence "Open your book, read and answer these questions" has gradually disappeared in schools. With the support of technology in the English foreign language (EFL) classroom and the development of new teaching methods, educational systems in countries around the world are being renewed and improved (Luaran, Sardi, Aziz, & Alias, 2015); and more importantly, in some under-developed countries, due to technology, children in rural schools have the opportunity to study with updated material and books.

The use of mobile devices inside and outside the classroom attracts more and more children and teenagers, even though most of them do not even own one. For this reason, many researchers (e.g. Abdul Fattah, 2015; Alamer and Al Khateeb, 2021; Al Saleem, 2013) have investigated ways of integrating them in various learning contexts, leading to a considerable amount of experiments on mobile learning. Burstson (2013) carried out an extensive review of the main MALL implementation studies in scientific journals, conference proceedings, project reports, and academic dissertations in order to offer an insight into the role of M-learning as played in various educational contexts.

WhatsApp is one of the technological advancements that is often used on specific mobile phones. Many texting applications were launched as cellphones grew more popular, but WhatsApp has become the most popular. Connection via mobile phones, notably WhatsApp messaging, has grown simpler, quicker, and less expensive (Han & Keskin, 2016). The following are the benefits of their implementations, according to Yalcinalp and Gulbahar (2010): Encourage learners to learn by forecasting needs and make collaborative learning effective and beneficial.

WhatsApp is particularly popular because its enhanced capabilities allow users to interact in various ways. For example, WhatsApp allows users to exchange text messages one-to-one or group conversations. Additionally, users can share documents and a variety of multimedia types as well as making voice or video calls. With this

functionality, WhatsApp is a useful learning tool that makes posting, sharing content and engaging in online discussions easy and available anywhere and anytime (Jain, Eddy Luanan, & Rahman, 2016).

One of the most interesting things about WhatsApp messaging and other popular technologies (text messaging, video games, etc.) is that they are potential learning tools (Dearstyne, 2011 Brown-Owens, Eason, & Lader, 2003). Educationalists can bind them to help students learn school-related content, as is shown by teachers who "encourage students to use messaging shorthand to spark their thinking processes" (Lee, 2002).

To take the benefit of adapting literateness education to the truth that electronic messaging is the dominant mode of written communication in the lives of many undergraduate students. Educationalists are to combine writing and electronic journals with improving students' writing skills (Raab, 2007). Teachers realize that when students are excited about their writing, they will care more about the final product (Rowen, 2005).

Alsaleem (2013) added new communicative applications such as WhatsApp should not be used just for the sake of wasting time and chatting. There has to be a goal that the teacher is trying to reach. It may help students in improving their writing products in a delightful way.

According to Mey (1998), language is an inseparable part of our daily life. It is a tool used to transmit messages and to communicate ideas, thoughts, and opinions. It is because of language that human being is situated in the society; language is a social phenomenon which creates and determines our position in different kinds of social networks and institutions. Culture is communication, vice versa because it influences social practices in general, and discourse in particular. Moreover, cultural factors play an important role in the development of diverse ways of talking and communicating. It can be said that there exists a certain, rule-governed linguistic behavior such as thanking, requesting and apologizing that allows us to deal with similar situations in similar ways across cultures.

Speech acts (SAs) are defined as acts performed by the speaker while making an utterance. The theory of SAs is a theory about what people set out to accomplish when they choose to speak. Searl (1975), the American language philosopher, believed that all linguistic communication involves linguistic SAs.

According to Searl (1975), a language is performing SAs such as making statement, giving command, asking question or making promises. Searle's approach holds that SAs are only explained by special conventions that are neither semantic nor pragmatic (in the sense of Grice's maxims of conversation).

Bayat (2013) states that "speech acts take part outside the language dimension of communication" (p.219). Language learners do not only acquire the grammar and vocabulary of a language, but they also learn how to use the speech acts of that language appropriately while communicating (Bayat, 2013). That is why understanding and producing speech acts is thought to be an indispensable constituent of a language learner's grammatical and social knowledge about learning a language and using the utterances appropriately in the target language (Bella, 2011).

Research problem

Being a teacher for ten years, the researcher has noticed that his students have difficulties in learning English as a foreign language, which might be due to the employment of conventional teaching techniques, which throw a shadow on students' English language performance. Students may lack confidence in their ability to use English because they are frightened of making mistakes and experiencing bashful sentiments in speech acts. The conventional instruction may unsuitable for assisting pupils in improving their English ability in speech acts. This has led the researcher to reflect on how speech acts can be taught more effectively, and thus, to investigate the effect of using WhatsApp chat on Jordanian EFL eleventh-grade students' speech acts performance.

Research hypothesis

The researcher assumes that using WhatsApp application may improve EFL students' speech acts performance.

Questions of the study

This study aims at answering the following question:

Are there any statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group due to the method of teaching (WhatsApp vs. conventional instruction) on eleventh-grade EFL students' performance in the speech acts post-test?

Operational definitions

The following terms have the designated meanings whenever they are used in the study:

Speech acts: an utterance by EFL learners who will say something and doing that thing such as asking, thanking, ordering, promising, requesting, warning, challenging, and threatening.

WhatsApp: an application which will be used by the researcher for sending messages to EFL learners (experimental group) during applying the experiment.

Performance: is the students' ability to produce and comprehend utterances efficiently and accurately in the target language.

Review of Related Literature

Empirical literature

Alamer (2021) investigated a study about the effects of using the WhatsApp application on language learners' motivation: a controlled investigation using structural equation modelling. The purpose of the study was to evaluate the extent to which the implementation of WhatsApp, and possibly other similar MALL applications, could be useful in understanding students' language learning motivation. The participants of the study were 447 undergraduate students from Saudi Arabia enrolled in the Department of English of two large public universities in the Eastern province, Saudi Arabia. The study adopted two instruments to obtain information about students' BPN and autonomous motivation. The second instrument was used to collect information about students' autonomous motivation. The result showed that using WhatsApp application can be useful in understanding students' language learning motivation.

Haron and Rahmat (2020) evaluated the use of mobile instant messaging tools to support teaching and learning in higher education. 66 students in Penang use smartphones with WhatsApp were assigned into experimental and control groups. Two instruments were used in this study to obtain the data which are pre and posttest and a questionnaire. The use of the WhatsApp application enables to improve learners' writing performance, classroom engagement, and academic achievement as well as enriches learners' writing that leads to a sustainable student.

Saleh (2019) examined the pedagogical role of WhatsApp as one of mobile-assisted language learning applications in developing motivational levels of Yemeni EFL learners to develop reading and writing skills. Twenty EFL undergraduate students of Aden University joined a WhatsApp English-medium chat group where they chatted, shared and commented on news articles in English for two months. Participants also took a pre-test and a post-test and responded to a questionnaire at the end of the study. Findings revealed that WhatsApp was a very effective application in developing students' motivation to improve their reading and writing skills. It helped them develop vocabulary, grammar, reading comprehension and writing.

Nurazizah, Friatin, and Sugiarto (2019) aimed at figuring out the teacher's way in implementing WhatsApp voice note in teaching speaking on narrative text and investigating the perspective on WhatsApp voice note to improve speaking skill on narrative text. The researcher used qualitative approach. This study involved 35 students of the tenth grade (X MIPA 1) and one English teacher. Instruments used in this study were classroom observation, interview, and questionnaire. The result of this study showed that learning to speak English using WhatsApp voice note is an attractive learning activity, positive activity, and WhatsApp voice note is easy to use.

Kartal (2019) investigated the empirical studies related to WhatsApp and language learning published in peer-reviewed journals. Thirty-seven studies were selected after a four-phase article identification procedure and a systematic review was conducted to investigate the effectiveness of WhatsApp on language learning. The results showed that WhatsApp has been used diversely in language learning. The studies found evidence that WhatsApp can be used to improve the four language skills (i.e. reading, listening, writing, and speaking), integrated language skills, and vocabulary.

Hashemifardnia, Namaziandost, and Rahimi Esfahani (2018) investigated the effects of using WhatsApp on Iranian EFL learners' vocabulary learning. To fulfil this objective, 50 Iranian female participants were selected among 80 students from Adiban English language institute, Baghmalek, Khuzestan, Iran. They were at the intermediate level of English proficiency based on the results of Oxford Quick Placement Test (OQPT). The results of paired samples and an independent samples t-test indicate that there was a significant difference

between the post-tests of the experimental and the control groups. The findings reveal that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group ($p < .05$) on the post-test.

Minalla (2018) examined the possibility of utilizing 'WhatsApp Group' in enhancing EFL learners' verbal interaction. To do this experimental and descriptive method were used to achieve the objective of this study. A questionnaire and pre- and post- test were adopted as tools for data collection. Samples of two groups (experimental & control) were randomly selected. The participants of the study were 30 learners. The analysis of the data revealed that the participants who underwent the voice messages on WhatsApp treatment significantly outperformed those who underwent in text messages on WhatsApp.

Ta'amneh (2017) investigated the effect of using "WhatsApp messenger" in learning the English language among university students during 2015/2016. The findings showed that integrating the WhatsApp application in teaching English language improved the EFL learner's abilities. It also showed that English lessons can be learned more effectively by integrating technological applications such as WhatsApp messenger to learn English than traditional methods.

Fattah (2015) investigated the effectiveness of using a WhatsApp Messenger as one of mobile learning technique to develop students' writing skills. Participants were 30 second year college students, English department from a private university in Saudi Arabia. The pre-post test comprised three questions, punctuate a paragraph, correct a paragraph and write an essay. Results of the t. test analysis revealed that WhatsApp technique yielded significant effects on students' writing skills, i.e. the experimental group outperformed the control group.

After reviewing the literature on using WhatsApp, most researchers stated that WhatsApp improves learners' reading, writing, listening and speaking skills such as Saleh (2019) and Nurazizah, Friatin, & Sugiarto (2019). However, none of them investigated the effect of using WhatsApp on Jordanian EFL eleventh-grade learners' speech acts performance and their attitudes toward it. WhatsApp may help the learners to improve their performance in speech acts in English such as expressing advice, giving instructions, warning, threat, regret, blame, complains, and excuses. Developing speech acts need practice; it cannot be developed in the classroom alone. Teachers should use WhatsApp to develop speech acts inside and outside the classroom.

Method

Participants of the Study

Two male scientific stream sections of Eleventh-grade students were randomly selected from a conveniently-selected school, namely; Fawzi Al-Mulki Secondary School for Boys, a public school in Al Mafrq Directorate of Education. The two sections were distributed into one experimental group and one control group. These two groups comprised 60 students who participated in this study which was conducted in the Second semester of the academic year 2021-2022.

The researcher selected Eleventh-grade in particular for two reasons: firstly, in Jordan, Tenth-grade is a critical stage because the students make the decision in what stream they will continue their secondary school in light of their GPA at the end of this grade, which is considered the final grade of the basic education. Similarly, twelfth grade is another critical stage in the student's academic life as according to their GPA they choose their major at the university. Secondly, as adults, the Eleventh-grade students in the assigned school under study have their own mobile phones, which are the learning platforms without which the hypothesis of the current study cannot be tested.

The participants were assigned into two groups: one experimental ($n=30$), and one control group ($n=30$). The two groups were administered to a pre-test, which showed equivalence in the results. Furthermore, learners took part in the pilot study of the instruments who were later excluded from the sample of the study. The one control group under the study was taught conventionally following the guidelines of the Teacher's Book while the one experimental group was taught through the proposed instructional program. Table 1 shows the total number of the participants in each group.

Table 1: The Distribution of the Participants of the Study

Group	Gender	Teaching method	Number of students
Control	Male	Conventional	30
Experimental	Male	WhatsApp	30

The current research addresses one question, mainly focusing on the effect of integrating WhatsApp as a teaching tool to develop EFL learners' speech acts performance compared to the conventional, face-to-face

method. To this end, the researcher adopted a quasi-experimental design which consisted of one dependent and one independent variables; the dependent variables are the participants' scores on the speech acts post-test w. In addition to the attitudes of the participants of the experimental group towards the integration of WhatsApp as a learning tool to improve their speech acts performance.

While the independent variables are that is the teaching method with which the participants were taught using WhatsApp as a teaching and learning platform.

Instruments of the Study

The researcher used was the speech acts achievement test. The pre-test sorted out the equivalence between groups established in the study and the degree of change in students' speech acts performance was measured as a result of the treatment. It was designed in light of the English language curriculum standards for developing the speech acts. The pre-test was administered at the beginning of the program when students were assigned one period of 45 minutes each and given a topic in the form of speech acts to determine their basic knowledge. The topic was selected from the textbook of secondary stage topic requirements.

Content Validity of the Test

In order to obtain the validity of the achievement test that was constructed by the researcher, a validation jury of eight university English professors and instructors at Yarmouk University were consulted to give their remarks and suggest any modifications to the test, if any. The jury's suggestions and comments were taken into consideration in modifying the test before its application.

Reliability of the Test

The internal consistency reliability method was obtained to judge how well the items on the test that were proposed to measure the same construct produce similar results. A test- retest pilot group that was excluded from the sample of the study was used within a two weeks' period. Then Pearson correlation was conducted. A statistical analysis calculated from the pair wise correlations between the two implementations of the test was used to measure the internal consistency. The correlation of the speech acts test-retest was 0.86, which means that the quality of the test is acceptable.

In order to make sure that the two groups of the study: Control and Experimental groups are equivalent; a speech acts proficiency pre-test was administered simultaneously to the groups. The researcher used descriptive statistics (Means, standard deviations and t-test) of students' scores of the control and experimental groups on the speech acts pre-test to identify any differences between the two groups, as shown in Table (2) and (3).

Table (2) Means, Standard deviation of the Students' Scores on the Pre-test

Group	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation
Conventional Instruction (Control)	30	25.46	7.569
WhatsApp (Experimental)	30	30.76	10.207

Table (3) T-test of the Students' Scores on the Pre-test

Group	Number	Mean	T	D.F	Sig
Conventional Instruction (Control)	30	25.46	-2.284	58	0.013
WhatsApp (Experimental)	30	30.76			

Data Analysis

In order to answer the first research question of the study, the data was analyzed quantitatively to determine the potential effect of WhatsApp on Jordanian Eleventh-grade EFL students' speech acts performance. Firstly, to measure if the proposed teaching tool of WhatsApp has an effect on the students' achievement on the post-test; a One-way ANCOVA test was used. Secondly, to compute the differences between the control and experimental groups on the pre- and the post-tests, a Paired Sample t-test was used.

Results of the Study

In order to answer the first question of the study, Are there any statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group due to the method of teaching (WhatsApp vs. conventional instruction) on eleventh-grade EFL students' performance in the speech acts post-test?

The researcher used a One-way Ancova to compare the means and standard deviation of student overall scores of the control and experimental groups on the writing post-test, as shown in Table (3).

Table (3) Means, Standard deviation of the Students' Scores on the Post-test

Group	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation
WhatsApp (Experimental)	30	49.10	13.869
Conventional Instruction (Control)	30	27.06	10.395
Total	60	38.08	16.46

Table (3) shows that there are differences between Mean of the post-test performance of the experimental group students and the control group. In order to find differences are statistically significant, One-way ANCOVA was used for eleventh-grade EFL students' performance in the speech acts (WhatsApp vs. conventional instruction). after Dropping the effect of their pre-measurement, and the following is a presentation of these results as shown in the table (4).

Table (4) Means, Standard deviation and One-way ANCOVA of the Students' Scores on the Post-test

Source	Sum of Squares	d.f	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Group	7033.566	1	7033.566	46.308	0.000	0.448
Error	8657.624	57	151.888			
Corrected Total	15994.583	59				

Table (4) shows that there are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) In the performance according to the teaching method (WhatsApp vs. conventional instruction), the value of (F) (46.308) with a statistical significance of (0.000), which is a statistically significant value, which means that there is an effect on developing the performance of the EFL Eleventh-Grade Students' Speech Acts attributed to the method of teaching (WhatsApp).

And table (4) Shows that the impact size of students' performance was large; The value of the Eta square (η^2) explained the percentage (44.8%) of the explained variance in the dependent variable, which is developing the performance of the EFL Eleventh-Grade Students' Speech Acts attributed to the method of teaching using WhatsApp.

Table (5) T-test to Compare the Means and Standard Deviation of Student Overall Scores of the Experimental Groups on the Writing Pre-test and Post-test

group	test	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	d.f	T	Sig
Experimental	Pre-test	30	30.76	10.207	28	-2.284	0.013
	Post-test	30	49.10	13.869			

Table (5) Shows that there are significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group due to teaching technique on EFL students' performance in speech acts.

Discussion

Through the results of the analysis, differences between the tribal and post-performance averages of the pilot group students taught by WhatsApp and the differences between the averages after the test performance and the control were found. It was also found that there are statistically significant differences at the indicative level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in performance by teaching method (WhatsApp versus traditional instructions) which means that there is an impact on the development of the performance of the 11th grade speech laws. - Classification of English as a foreign language students attributable to teaching method (WhatsApp).

The magnitude of the impact on students' performance was also significant, meaning the development of speech law performance for 11th-grade students in English as a foreign language is due to the teaching method using WhatsApp. Thus, there are statistically significant differences between the averages of the experimental group's grades and the control group attributable to the teaching method in the performance of English as a foreign language in pronunciation acts. It is clear from the foregoing that text messages "SMS" and texts in IM instant messaging are Verbal Messages text-based verbal messages and are therefore subject to the characteristics and

features of texts in terms of composition and contextual connotation Semantic Context. There are also content-related variables including audio, image, text, video, notes, etc.

Learning English for non-TEFL speakers needs an attractive teaser environment and continuity of communication and interaction that can be achieved through the use of modern technology available in the hands of the majority of learners; the technique requires the provision of possibilities that help to learn and accomplish tasks in the same and superior way as the traditional educational environment. This finding agreed with Saleh (2019), who reported that WhatsApp was a very effective application in developing students' motivation to improve their reading and writing skills. Help them develop vocabulary, grammar, and reading and writing skills. It also agreed with Harun and Rahmat (2020), who noted that using WhatsApp enables learners to improve their writing performance, class engagement, and academic achievement, as well as enrich their writing, leading to student sustainability. Kartal (2019) found evidence that WhatsApp can be used to improve the four language skills (i.e., reading, listening, writing, and speaking); integrated language skills; and vocabulary.

Conclusion

The findings have shown that WhatsApp is a potential catalyst for speech acts performance. As mobile devices are finding their way into the language classroom, many learning opportunities are unlocked for EFL learners alike.

Language educators should take advantage of the capabilities afforded by technology for teaching speech acts. The findings, albeit small-scale in sample and duration, are hoped to provide insights into the utility of integrating mobile technologies into foreign language teaching and learning.

However, the role of mobile technologies in the language classroom should not be overstated, as technology, albeit a catalyst for innovation, is not a fix-it-all for all learning dilemmas and in all learning contexts. The success of mobile learning is contingent upon a conducive learning environment and a diligent teacher who is willing to take risks and venture beyond the boundaries of traditional instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the results, the study recommends the following:

1. Enhance, the teacher used the features of WhatsApp interchangeably.
2. Enabling the use of WhatsApp for educational materials, class work, homework, and discussion makes it easier.
3. Expansion of research related to mobile education, screen and text variants, interaction patterns, and interface interaction.
4. Conducting similar studies that seek to know the effectiveness of the WhatsApp application in developing other types of learning, such as cooperative learning, among English-language students at different levels.
5. Supporting group interaction and joint work, which has become a requirement of education through social networks.

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